

THE IMPORTANCE OF PHYSICAL DEVELOPMENT IN A CHILD'S LIFE

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Abstract: This article briefly mentions the place, importance and health impact of physical development in a child's life.

Keywords: psychological health, physical health, anomaly, health, functional indicator.

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Children's adaptive skills are also taken into account by pediatricians at each stage of child development as an indicator of health. Therefore, various children's institutions reduce or increase the anatomical and physiological characteristics of children, their susceptibility to certain factors, the body's resistance at certain age periods. Thus, the development of motor skills of speech is taken into account when examining children of early and preschool age. What are the main indicators of physical health of children and adolescents Physical development of children and adolescents is one of the most important indicators of health [2.6.7]. How well the child has developed is determined by periodic medical examinations in medical institutions or schools.

Almost from birth, each child's height, body weight, and chest circumference are measured. The obtained results provide an opportunity to see the general picture of the development of the child's body. In addition, the main indicators of children's physical health are the following conditions: teeth, mucous membranes of the eyes, oral cavity, skin condition, maturity level for the subject's age, body fat i. Functional indicators are also important during the examination. For this, the vital capacity of the lungs, the muscle strength of the arms and the spine are measured. The following factors influence the indicators of the health assessment of children and adolescents: the results of measurements and weighing; biological age; neuropsychic development.

Due to the uneven growth of the skeleton during childhood, the proportions of the body also change. If in adulthood we have preserved the proportions of the neonatal period, it is very bad! A newborn baby has a relatively large head - it accounts for a quarter of its total growth, short arms and legs. In an adult, the height of the head is one tenth of the length of the body. The median point of the

newborn baby corresponds to the navel, and in the adult, it is on the projection of the pubis. The calculation of various proportionality indices helps the doctor to accurately determine the biological age of the child and its compatibility with the passport. One of the proportionality indices can be very easily used by parents at home to determine whether it is time to send a child to school [1,13,]. This is called the Philippine test: the child is asked to try to reach the tip of the opposite ear through the top of the head without bending the head. If the child does not reach his ears, then his brain is not yet mature enough to absorb the curriculum. In addition, if the baby does not have one permanent tooth, parents should seriously consider sending their child to the first grade.

For such children, the school load can be unbearable, which leads to health problems. Philippine Test Growth can also be significantly affected by climatic and geographical conditions. It turns out that the greatest activity of growth, like everything in the wild, occurs in spring and summer, and in autumn and winter, the child does not grow so intensively. People tend to be shorter in colder climates and at higher altitudes. It should also not be forgotten that the final growth is influenced by a person's belonging to certain ethnic groups. The growth rates of the child's organs and tissue systems are different. In contrast to this curve of general somatic growth, the brain grows rapidly only in the first years of life and reaches almost adult size by the age of five[4,6,9]. The growth curve of immune lymphoid tissue is very significantly different from the rest, its relative mass reaches 200% in the period from 3 to 6-7 years. This is a normal age-related physiological reaction of lymphoid tissue hypertrophy, and enlarged lymph nodes can be felt in a child.

Indicators of comprehensive assessment of children's health status depend on such criteria as the presence or absence of chronic diseases at the time of the survey; the condition of the main organs and systems (blood circulation, breathing, cardiovascular, nervous, etc.); the level of harmony of physical and neuropsychic development. Physical health indicators of children and adolescents are recorded by pediatricians, district doctors or medical staff of pre-school and pre-school educational institutions during routine examinations. In other words, it is no longer enough for the doctor to determine whether the child has any disease during the examination. It is important to maximize the range of indicators responsible for the development of biological and social functions of the growing body, timely detection of chronic diseases. The physical state of children's health and its indicators cannot be imagined without knowing how the child's nervous system works, how the development of vision, hearing, memory, attention, speech and thinking is [10,12]. As an indicator of children's health, physical development should be supplemented with information about psychological status. Early detection of abnormalities and sending the child to specialists is an important task

of the pediatrician. Children's psychological health has always been given attention from an early age, because it is a necessary condition for the development of a full-fledged person. Mental health is inextricably linked with physical health. Psychological health of a person is a connection between the internal harmony of the body, emotions, thoughts and external harmony - between the person himself and the outside world, society. The main indicators of children's psychological health are expressed in the following criteria:

- the ability to understand oneself and the people around;
- realizing one's potential in various activities;
- the ability to make a conscious and correct choice;
- in a state of mental comfort;
- normal social behavior.

From a scientific point of view, this is the most important component, without which human success cannot be imagined, including physical, psychological and social well-being, the absence of any discomfort, illness and disease. Normative indicators of children's and adolescents' health allow not only the successful growth and development of a person being formed, but also to be socially active, to perform all the functions and tasks assigned to him [9,11]. It follows that the success and well-being of society and the state, as well as the national security of the country, depend on the health of the young generation. According to statistics, the main indicators of children's health have decreased several times over the last ten years. Thus, today about 30% of primary school students have one or another deviation in their health. About 12% of schoolchildren have myopia, 17% have height disorders, and 40% have visual acuity. Currently, doctors distinguish three main components of health: physical, psychological, behavioral. The physical component refers to the development of organs and systems of the body, their condition, activity, as well as the level of growth. Psychological component - psycho-emotional state, mental activity, social needs of a person, adequacy of behavior in society. The behavioral component is the manifestation of one's condition, the ability to communicate, feelings, mood, the existence of a life position and the desire to benefit society. Children's adaptive abilities are also taken into account by pediatricians at each stage of child development as an indicator of health [4,7,6]. Therefore, various children's institutions reduce or increase the anatomical and physiological characteristics of children, their susceptibility to certain factors, the body's resistance at certain age periods. Thus, the development of motor skills of speech is taken into account when examining children of early and preschool age.

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